

CLINICAL INTERVIEWING MICROSKILLS FRAMEWORK[©] Observation & Self-evaluation (v. 2)

Name of Interviewer: _____ Date: _____

Name of Observer: _____ Time: _____

Interview's duration: _____

	inappropriate use			appropriate use		
1. Use of interviewee's name						
2. Eye contact						
3. Facial expressions						
4. Head nods						
5. Body posture						
6. Gestures						
7. Distance / Level						
8. Tone of voice						
9. Grammatical style						
10. Minimal encouragers						
11. Verbal tracking						
12. Non-interruptions						
13. Silence						
14. Keyword restatements						
15. Restatements						
16. Paraphrases						
17. Open questions/Probes						
18. Reflections of feelings						
19. Summarization						

Strengths:

Thoughts for improvement:

General comments:

[optional] Carkhuff & Truax Ratings Scales:

Congruence: ____

Empathy: ____

Unconditional positive regard: ____

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